

ESSAY

Open Problems in Computational Historical Linguistics

[version 1; peer review: 2 approved, 1 approved with reservations]

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V1 First published: 20 Nov 2023, 3:201
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.16804.1>

Latest published: 20 Nov 2023, 3:201
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.16804.1>

Abstract

Problems constitute the starting point of all scientific research. The essay reflects on the different kinds of problems that scientists address in their research and discusses a list of 10 problems for the field of computational historical linguistics, that was proposed throughout 2019 in a series of blog posts. In contrast to problems identified in different contexts, these problems were considered to be solvable, but no solution could be proposed back then. By discussing the problems in the light of developments that have been made in the field during the past five years, a modified list is proposed that takes new insights into account but also finds that the majority of the problems has not yet been solved.

Plain language summary

This essay elaborates on ten problems for the field of historical linguistics, dealing with the evolution of languages, which have so far not been solved. It is argued that the solution of these problems is possible, but that additional work is needed before breakthroughs can be made.

Keywords

historical linguistics, computational linguistics, open problems, scientific problem solving

This article is included in the [Horizon 2020 gateway](#).

Open Peer Review

Approval Status

	1	2	3
version 1 20 Nov 2023	 view	 view	 view

1. **Jeff Good** , University of Buffalo, Buffalo, USA

2. **Thomas Brochhagen** , Universitat Pompeu Fabra, Barcelona, Spain

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This article is included in the [Linguistic Diversity](#) collection.

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Author roles: List JM: Conceptualization, Formal Analysis, Funding Acquisition, Investigation, Project Administration, Resources, Visualization, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing

Competing interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Grant information: This project has received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the [European Unions Horizon Europe research and innovation programme] (Grant agreement No. 101044282).

The funders had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript.

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How to cite this article: List JM. **Open Problems in Computational Historical Linguistics [version 1; peer review: 2 approved, 1 approved with reservations]** Open Research Europe 2023, 3:201 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.16804.1>

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Introduction

The driving force of all scientific inquiries are problems – unsolved or *open problems*. We observe phenomena that we cannot explain, we do not understand how phenomena interact and to which degree they influence each other, or we want to know how we can enhance methods that allow us to study phenomena of interest. While questions that ask for the solution of big problems often trigger peoples' initial interest in science, scientists themselves typically work with much smaller problems. While the solution of small problems may seem boring to the public, they are crucial for the field to advance and they can lay the foundation for major breakthroughs at later stages.

Working on the typically small problems that individual subfields offer, all scientists run the risk of losing track of their discipline's broader challenges. Working luckily in our ivory tower that shields us from the outside world, it is often through confrontation with laypeople or scientists from other fields that we are made aware of the greater challenges of our own discipline.

In the field of linguistics, specifically in the field of historical linguistics, one of the questions that linguists have stopped asking is how language – that is, the specific communicative faculty of which many think is unique to humans – originated for the first time. Non-linguists are often very surprised that asking for the origin of language is a taboo question in the field of historical linguistics. Already in the 19th century, the question had been officially banned from the agenda of most linguistic endeavors. The *statuts* of the *Société de Linguistique de Paris* from 1866, for example, state that '[the] Société does not accept any contributions concerning neither the origin of the language faculty, nor the creation of a universal

language.' ([Société de Linguistique de Paris, 1871, III](#)).¹ The situation has not changed since then. One of the first things I learned as a student of Indo-European and Comparative Linguistics at the Freie Universität Berlin in 2003 was that serious historical linguists would never ask about the origin or evolution of language.

Of course, there are good reasons to avoid asking how language originated. When sifting through the literature that has been published on this matter, one finds a diverse collection ranging from serious attempts to summarize what we can know and what we can't know, up to the weirdest speculations. There are not many similar fields in science where it is so difficult to draw a line between genius and madness. On the one hand, one finds researchers who meticulously assemble tiniest pieces of evidence in the search for a clear picture in the dark glasses. On the other hand, one finds scholars so obsessed with a single idea that they have become blind to counterarguments. Specifically for outsiders from the field, for those not trained in historical linguistics and evolutionary anthropology, it is often very difficult to tell if a theory on the origin of language should be treated as a serious or a senseless idea. Next to Johann Gottfried Herder (1744–1802) who imagined that human beings would have run through the woods imitating the sounds of the objects and phenomena surrounding them ([Herder, 1778](#), see also [Table 1](#)), scholars discuss whether Neanderthals could speak or not ([Dediu & Levinson, 2013](#)), they debate whether a single gene was responsible for our language faculty ([Atkinson et al., 2018](#)), they propose that research on aphasia might

¹ My translation, original text: La Société n'admet aucune communication concernant, soit l'origine du langage, soit la création d'une langue universelle.

Table 1. Collection of quotes on the origin of language.

Sound imitation at the origin of language.
<i>Take for example the sheep. As an image [...] – how much, how difficult to discern! All characteristics are intertwined, next to each other, all still unspeakable! Who can talk shape? Who can sound colors? [...] Who can say what he feels with his hands? But listen, the sheep bleats! [...] "Ha!" says the apprentice [...], "now I will recognize you – you bleat!" The turtledove coos! The dog barks! There are three words, because he was looking for three clear ideas, the latter go into his logic, the former into his dictionary! [...] The soul grasped [for it] – there it has a sounding word! (Herder, 1778, 76).²</i>
Yin, yang, and the language of proto-sapiens.
<i>The Proto-Sapiens grammar was so simple that the sporadic references in previous paragraphs have essentially described it. The prime importance of sound symbolism for the people of nature should be noted again before we further detail that the vowel E was felt as indicating the "yin" element, passivity, femininity etc., while "O" indicated the yang element, activeness, masculinity etc.; "A" was neutral or spiritual, indicating things conceived by the mind and emotions rather than with the physical senses. (Papakitsos & Kenanidis, 2018, 8)</i>

² My translation, original text: Da ist z. E. das Schaf. Als Bild [schwebet es dem Auge mit allen Gegenständen, Bildern und Farben auf einer großen Naturtafel vor] wie viel, wie mühsam zu unterscheiden! Alle Merkmale sind fein verflochten, nebeneinander alle noch unaussprechlich! Wer kann Gestalt reden? Wer kann Farben tönen? [Er nimmt das Schaf unter seine tastende Hand das Gefühl ist sicherer und voller, aber so voll, so dunkel ineinander.] Wer kann, was er fühlt, sagen? Aber horch! das Schaf blöket! [Da reißt sich ein Merkmal von der Leinwand des Farbenbildes, worin so wenig zu unterscheiden war, von selbst los, ist tief und deutlich in die Seele gedrungen.] »Ha!« sagt der lernende [Unmündige wie jener Blindgewesene Cheseldens.] »nun werde ich dich wiederkennen du blökst!« Die Turteltaube girt! Der Hund bellet! Da sind drei Worte, weil er drei deutliche Ideen versuchte, diese in seine Logik, jene in sein Wörterbuch! [Vernunft und Sprache taten gemeinschaftlich einen furchtsamen Schritt, und die Natur kam ihnen auf halbem Wege entgegen durchs Gehör. Sie tönnte das Merkmal nicht bloß vor, sondern tief in die Seele hinein! Es klang!] Die Seele haschte da hat sie ein tönendes Wort!]

shed light on the structure of early language (Code, 2021), and they speculate about the nature of the ‘language of proto-sapiens’ in the context of *yin* and *yang* (Papakitsos & Kenanidis, 2018, see also Table 1). There is no doubt: the question invites bold speculation, and when bold speculation becomes careless, it can easily damage the reputation of entire scientific fields. At the same time, however, it feels strange that linguists would deliberately decide to ignore the investigation of a problem that some might consider the most fascinating the field has to offer. While following inconclusive debates and trying to not get angry or amused by weird speculations regarding the “big questions” of one’s discipline, one may easily forget that there *are* valid and important problems which one may have forgotten to think about. An example for such a problem that is routinely ignored in historical linguistics is the problem of the “size” of a language. While historical linguists never ask how many words a language has, or how many sentences one can speak until one would repeat oneself, non-linguists have often asked me these questions. I still remember quite vividly how annoyed I always felt – and at times even reacted – when colleagues from biology asked me if English was bigger than German or French. I tried to explain that languages are open systems that cannot be measured by counting the words in a corpus and that if at all, one would have to count the words in the head of individuals, but that this would not be possible from a practical viewpoint, and that as a result of these complications, linguists preferred to ignore the question completely and look into other problems instead. But with time, I learned to put my linguistic pride aside and began to understand that a solution to the question would have several important implications to other questions that are of vital interest to my research.

In evolutionary biology, for example, scholars have argued that the amount of genes that were horizontally transferred among species largely exceeds the amount of genes that were vertically inherited (Dagan & Martin, 2006). Horizontal transfer is quite abundant in language history as well, and we usually base our phylogenetic studies on very small collections of basic words often not even exceeding 200 items per language (Greenhill *et al.*, 2023; Sagart *et al.*, 2019). It would therefore be interesting to have a rough estimate of how many words of a language survive over time, but this would require (at the very least) a rough estimate of the words that constitute a language.

In historical linguistics, Starostin (1989) has proposed that every language has about 1000 lexical roots from which most of the words in the language are formed. Up to today, no attempt has been made to count the number of lexical roots, even for well-documented languages like German or Chinese. It would be very interesting to see if Starostin’s estimate holds cross-linguistically, and how much variation we should expect when comparing the languages of the world.

Given that languages may differ quite substantially regarding the way in which they build new words from existing ones, it would also be very interesting to see to which degree languages differ regarding the “productivity” of their words to form families (List, 2023), and to which degree the production of new

vocabulary is triggered by external events, such as, for example, pandemics or wars.

Lastly, measuring the number of words that different speakers of the same language know might even help us to investigate to which degree individual language faculties vary among humans. The question to which degree speakers of the same language differ regarding their competence is another question that is – unfortunately – rarely asked, although the notion of competence plays a crucial role in some linguistic fields.³

While the question of the “size of a language” has been mostly ignored in the context of historical linguistics, vocabulary size or vocabulary breadth⁴ have been routinely investigated by scholars focusing on foreign language acquisition (Milton, 2009) and psycholinguistics (Brybaert *et al.*, 2016; Nation & Coxhead, 2021). Unfortunately, the majority of these studies has concentrated exclusively on English. We know that languages may differ quite substantially regarding the structure of their word families and the techniques they use to create new words from existing ones (Milton, 2010, 226, see also List *et al.*, 2016b, 9f). As a result, the estimates on vocabulary size are of limited use to address the above-mentioned problems in historical linguistics, and it remains an open problem to measure and compare the size of the vocabularies of the world’s languages.

As scientists, we cannot ask enough questions. Being used to address small problems as part of our scientific routines, however, we may forget to ask the “big questions” that are at the heart of our particular disciplines. By ignoring certain questions deliberately and limiting the scope of questions we allow ourselves to ask in our work we may easily lose the chance us to enrich our studies and open new horizons. Specifically for young and rapidly growing subdisciplines such as the field of computational historical linguistics, it can be very helpful to identify particular problems and challenges that should be addressed in future work. In the following, I will reflect on challenges that have been discussed in the context of comparative linguistics and contrast them with those challenges that I have identified for my own work. In doing so, I hope to show that an active discussion about open problems can be a useful guiding principle not only for an entire research field, but also for individual researchers.

Rational, general and historical problems

Major problems and challenges for the field of comparative linguistics have been discussed in the past on different occasions. Weinreich *et al.* (1968, 183–187) identify five general problems with respect to the phenomenon of language change, which they call

³ See Dąbrowska, 2020 for a rare example where scholars try to deal with differences in competence, investigating genitive marking in Polish.

⁴ The term *vocabulary breadth* is usually understood as “the number of words a learner knows in a foreign language” (Milton, 2010, 211), but it can probably also be used as a term denoting the number of words a native speaker knows.

- (1) the *constraints problem*, dealing with the question of which changes are possible in language change and which conditions could constrain them,
- (2) the *transition problem*, dealing with the question of how and where changes are instantiated in concrete during language change,
- (3) the *embedding problem*, dealing with the systemic aspects conditioning language change,
- (4) the *evaluation problem*, dealing with the question to which degree change happens consciously in a community of language users, and
- (5) the *actuation problem*, dealing with the question of how changes are triggered.

Roberts and Sneller (2020) discuss these in the context of the “four questions” for evolutionary sciences proposed by Tinbergen (1963), pointing to potential empirical implications and programs for future research. Tinbergen’s questions themselves have been originally stated for the field of biological evolution (Bateson & Laland, 2013), although they were later adopted by researchers studying cultural evolution (Roberts & Sneller, 2020, 194f). They are nowadays usually presented in a more systematic fashion than the problems by Weinreich *et al.* (1968), distinguishing two major perspectives, *dynamic* (diachronic) and *static* (synchronic), and two major kinds of questions, *how-* and *why-*questions, the former referring to individuals and the latter to species (Tinbergen, 1963). This allows to look at particular problems (e.g., the evolution of a specific trait) from four perspectives, namely

- (1) the perspective of the *ontogeny*, focusing on how the trait evolves in individuals,
- (2) the perspective of the *mechanism*, focusing on how the trait is structured synchronically in an individual,
- (3) the perspective of the *phylogeny*, focusing on how the trait evolves inside a given species, and
- (4) the perspective of the *function*, focusing on the role adaptive role the trait plays for a given species.

Similar to Roberts and Sneller (2020), I do not find it very helpful to try to classify the five problems by Weinreich *et al.* (1968) according to the schema proposed by Tinbergen (1963). Despite the apparent systematicity of the latter, I find the schema hard to apply to concrete problems.

As yet another example for an attempt to systematize linguistic endeavor by stating problems, Eugenio Coseriu (1921–2002, see Coseriu, 1973, 65f) suggested to distinguish three basic problems of language change, namely

- (a) the rational problem of change (“problema racional del cambio”),
- (b) the general problem of change events (“problema general de los cambios”), and
- (c) the historical problem of a given change (“problema histórico de tal cambio determinado”).

These problems can again be represented by certain questions, as indicated by Coseriu himself. The rational problem asks why languages change after all (“¿por que cambian las lenguas?”). This question does not find a counterpart in the list of problems proposed by Weinreich *et al.* (1968), where language change has been taken for granted, and the goal is to investigate and describe the phenomenon. As Coseriu emphasizes himself, the problem is of a chiefly *theoretical* nature and cannot be resolved by identifying all causes for particular changes that can be observed for particular languages (ibid. 66f), but rather addresses the deeper question of why mutability is one of the fundamental characteristics of language (68f). Coseriu himself sees the reason for the mutable character of language as a result of the fact that languages is constantly recreated, not only when being learned by speakers, but also when being applied by them (69f).

The second problem of Coseriu is similar to the *actuation problem* by Weinreich *et al.* (1968), addressing the question in which conditions certain changes occur (“¿en qué condiciones suelen ocurrir cambios en las lenguas?”). In Coseriu’s view, this problem is a problem of *general linguistics* in the sense that general linguistics deals with linguistic phenomena independently of particular languages. Particular changes in particular languages, finally, are addressed by the third problem, which Coseriu calls *historical*, emphasizing the individual character of investigating particular changes in particular languages.

Coseriu’s strict distinction between *general problems* in linguistics on the one hand and *historical problems* on the other hand finds a very close counterpart in the distinction between *p(articular language)-linguistics* and *g(eneral) linguistics* by Haspelmath (2020, 5), where a distinction between the investigation of language as a general communication system and the investigation of individual languages is made (see also Haspelmath, 2019).

Judging from numerous discussions with colleagues, distinguishing questions applying to individual languages and language families from questions applying to language in general (as a system of human communication) constitutes a much more important systematization of problems than the attempts by Weinreich *et al.* and Tinbergen. The failure to distinguish questions pertaining to particular languages and questions pertaining to language in general has led to many misunderstandings in the field of comparative linguistics. In my own research, it has happened quite a few times that scholars who reviewed my work were asking me to test new methods which I had designed to account for general problems of spoken languages against methods that could only solve problems for particular languages.

Hilbert problems

At the end of 2018, students from the Universidad de Buenos Aires asked me about the biggest challenges for computational historical linguistics. Inspired by this discussion, I decided to make a short list of tasks that I consider challenging, but of which I still think could be solved some time in the nearer or farther future.

The idea to make such a list of questions is not new. Mathematicians, for example, have their well-known *Hilbert Problems*,

proposed by David Hilbert in 1900 (published in Hilbert, 1902). In linguistics, I first heard about them from Russell D. Gray, who himself was introduced to this by a talk of the linguist Martin Hilpert, who gave a talk on challenging questions for linguistics in 2014, called “Challenges for 21st century linguistics”. Russell D. Gray since then has emphasized the importance to propose “Hilbert” questions for the fields of comparative linguistics and cultural evolution, and has also presented his own challenges in the past.

Due to my methodological background, the problems I identified and assembled were by no means big and in some sense also not necessarily extremely challenging (at least not at first sight). Instead, the problems I selected were problems I wanted to see solved at that time. While the solution of the problems would not directly advance our knowledge about language evolution and linguistic typology, I had the hope that it would help us to do so indirectly, by giving us the possibility to assemble more data and to carry out new analyses that would ultimately help us to search for answers on deeper questions in historical linguistics in specific and in comparative linguistics in general.

One further aspect of the problems that I selected was that I was convinced that they could *all* be solved by algorithms or workflows. Characterizing them as “small” refers to their very specific application range. I did not want to express that the problems I selected were not challenging. It also did not mean that I expected that they all could be solved in the nearer future, although, given that the work in the field of computational and computer-assisted language comparison, is steadily progressing, I had some confidence that at least some of these problems that I assembled by then would indeed be solvable within the next five years.

When writing down my ten open problems for computational historical linguistics, I announced them in a blog post for the blog *The Genealogical World of Phylogenetic Networks* (<https://phylonetworks.blogspot.com/>), edited by David Morrison, in January 2019 (List, 2019a), with the plan of discussing each of the problems in detail in monthly blog posts throughout the year. I managed to stick with this schedule and concluded the year with a final blog post in December 2019, in which I looked back at one year of discussing problems in my own research for which no solution could have been found by then (List, 2019d).

The 10 problems I came up with are listed in Table 2. I divided the problems into three different groups, which roughly correspond to three different categories I identified as being important for research in general, namely *modeling* (m), *inference* (i), and *analysis* (a). This triad, inspired by Dehmer et al. (2011, XVII), follows the general idea that scientific research in the historical disciplines usually starts from some kind of idea we have about our research object (the *model* stage), and based on which we then apply methods to infer examples in our data which confirm our ideas (the *inference* stage). Having inferred enough examples, we can then *analyze* them qualitatively or quantitatively (the *analysis* stage) and use this information to update our model, as indicated in the schema in Figure 1.

Table 2. 10 problems of computational diversity linguistics discussed in a series of blog posts in 2019.

No.	Problem
1	automated morpheme segmentation (i)
2	automated borrowing detection (i)
3	automated sound law induction (i)
4	automated phonological reconstruction (i)
5	simulating lexical change (m)
6	simulating sound change (m)
7	statistical proof of language relatedness (m)
8	typology of semantic change (a)
9	typology of sound change (a)
10	typology of semantic promiscuity (a)

Figure 1. Research workflow for the investigation of problems in computational historical linguistics.

As an example for this procedure, consider the problem of *cognate detection*, the detection of historically related – or homologous – words across languages. Here, initial surveys of words across different languages have long since confirmed that we can easily find words which are to some extent similar to each other with respect to their form and their meaning, and that the amount of similar words varies quite significantly from one pair of languages to another. Starting from a model of *lexical change* that states that the lexicon of all spoken languages changes slowly over time, be it through the change of individual sounds or through the change of the meaning which a word expresses, we can derive a model of *language split* which assumes that the same language may split into two or more varieties when its speakers separate from each other and their language keeps modifying independently. Based on this evolutionary model, we can then conclude that similar words observed across different language varieties have been inherited from the common, formerly unified, ancestral variety. In order to detect these *cognates*, one could now design methods that help to find more than the so far observed similar words in order to increase the data basis. Once this has been done, and more material has been identified, one can

analyze the data and try to see if the analysis provides some hints on specific questions, such as, for example, the more detailed branching history of a given language family.

As one can see from the example, the term *modeling* is used in a rather loose sense, unlike its usage in phylogenetic approaches, where *modeling* is often treated as synonymous with *stochastic modeling*, referring to a transition matrix which shows how certain characters can turn into other characters during an evolutionary process (Nunn, 2011).

With respect to my ten open problems from 2019, the first four problems belong to the family of inference problems, since they all deal with tasks where something has to be inferred from the data, be it morphemes from words (Problem 1, List, 2019e), lexical borrowings from word lists (Problem 2, List, 2019g), sound laws from data on ancestral languages and their descendants (Problem 3, List, 2019f), or proto-forms from cognate sets (Problem 4, List, 2019h).

The next three problems in my list belong to the family of modeling problems, since they all require to understand the processes by which certain aspects of languages, such as their lexicon (Problem 5, List, 2019i) or their sound systems (Problem 6, List, 2019j) change over time. Proving language relatedness statistically (Problem 7, List, 2019k) does not directly model any aspect of language evolution, but it requires a model of language relatedness that can then be tested against a random model in which languages are thought to be unrelated.⁵

The last three problems in my list all had “typology” in their title. They belong to the family of analysis problems, aiming to gain insights into phenomena of language change by comparing major processes, such as semantic change (Problem 8, List, 2019l) and sound change (Problem 9, List, 2019b). What was meant by “typology” in this context was a data-driven estimate of the overall cross-linguistic dynamics of these phenomena. Lacking consistent accounts on the general tendencies of these processes and phenomena when excluding areal and genetic factors, the task I thought of was to come up with a consistent estimate on each of them. While semantic change and sound change are probably self-explaining in this context, the last problem – dealing with the question of what I called “semantic promiscuity” by then – deserves some explanation (Problem 10, List, 2019c). What I meant with this term was the degree to which certain words, due to their original meanings, are re-used or re-cycled in the

human lexicon. While the term *promiscuity* has been used before in other contexts in linguistics (Schweikhard, 2018), the specific usage of promiscuity to denote what one could also call *semantic productivity* or *concept productivity*, was first proposed in List *et al.* (2016a), where biological and linguistic processes were consistently compared with each other, and semantic promiscuity was identified as a phenomenon similar to *domain promiscuity* in protein evolution in biology (Basu *et al.*, 2008), with an explicit analogy being identified between the processes of *word formation* in linguistics and *protein assembly* (Ahnert *et al.*, 2015) in biology (List *et al.*, 2016a, 5).

New and old open problems

The series of blog posts was generally well received, and some posts triggered interesting discussions. However, my hope that at least a few of the problems might be considered as “solved” after half a decade turned out to have been a false one. When looking back at the list of ten problems now, almost five years after I first proposed them, I do not have the feeling that we got any closer in solving any of them.

Inference problems

As far as inference problems are concerned, no significant progress was made with respect to the tasks of automated morpheme segmentation (Problem 1) and automated sound law induction (Problem 3).

Quite a few new methods have been proposed to address the detection of lexical borrowings (Problem 2). Among these are supervised approaches (which I had deliberately excluded, since I consider unsupervised approaches as more useful when it comes to inference problems) that made use of recurrent neural networks (Miller *et al.*, 2020), there are tree-based approaches that even try to identify the direction of borrowings (Neureiter *et al.*, 2022),⁶ and there are numerous attempts to handle very specific cases of lexical borrowing, such as contact across language families (Hantgan *et al.*, 2022; List & Forkel, 2022) or contact induced by dominant languages (Kaiping & Klamer, 2022; Miller & List, 2023).

While all of these methods may contribute to the detection of borrowings in particular cases, all of them suffer from the problem that they need very specific conditions to work. For supervised approaches, we need labeled training data, for tree-based approaches to borrowing detection, we need phylogenetic trees, for borrowing detection across language families, we need languages to belong to different families, and for the detection of borrowing from dominant languages, we need to deal with languages that are spoken in a region where dominant languages occur.

It is well possible, that the current pocket knife solution that employs various forms of evidence to find borrowings in very specific contexts is the only feasible way to handle the

⁵ While there are numerous attempts in the literature to come up with a convincing statistical model to prove genetic relationship (Baxter & Manaster Ramer, 2000; Blevins & Sproat, 2021; Ceolin, 2019; Kassian *et al.*, 2015; Kessler, 2001; Mortarino, 2009; Ringe, 1992), none of the attempts which have been proposed so far deals with lexical comparisons in all their complexity. Either, scholars only compare initial consonants with each other (Kessler, 2001; Ringe, 1992), or they resort to sound classes (Baxter & Manaster Ramer, 2000; Kassian *et al.*, 2015), and even if scholars compute random models for whole alignments of potentially related words (List, 2014), they have the problem of not accounting for the factor of closeness due to borrowing.

⁶ I write “try”, since the study does not provide a detailed error analysis and many directions seem to be problematic).

problem of language contact in computational historical linguistics. Even classical approaches to historical language comparison do not use one unified approach to identify borrowed traits, but rather hope to accumulate enough evidence until borrowing is the only convincing solution to explain the data at hand. But even if we accept that we need to embrace arguments based on “cumulative evidence” (Berg, 1998) or “consilience” (Whewell, 1847; Wilson, 1998) in order to solve the problem of borrowing detection (see also List, 2019n, 11), we are still quite far away from being able to handle all the evidence with automated approaches which goes into the argumentation of classical qualitative approaches to borrowing detection. From today’s perspective, I would adjust the problem of borrowing detection in order to make it more specific. Here, a problem I would really love to be solved would be the detection of the *layers of contact* across a group of languages (Lee & Sagart, 2008). Contact layers have been discussed for a long time in the literature on language contact. The idea behind contact layers is that the individual traits of a language can be *stratified* and assigned to different groups that would point to different phases in which these traits were borrowed through specific contact events. Developing a method that would be able to group borrowings into different strata that could then be identified with specific contact events in time would be extremely beneficial for the discipline of historical linguistics. The problem is, however, also very challenging, since it is not clear whether contact layers *can* be identified in all cases (evidence might just have been lost), and on what kind of evidence one should base the detection of contact layers. This makes contact layer detection a truly hard problem, although I would not consider it impossible to solve.

Rather huge progress – at least when looking back specifically at the last couple of years – has been made with respect to supervised phonological reconstruction. Here the task is different from the problem I had originally stated. Instead of inferring the proto-language from a sufficiently large number of aligned cognate sets, the method is given aligned cognate sets (or simply cognate sets) along with a certain number of already reconstructed proto-forms that can be used to train a machine learning model in a first instance. In a second instance the model can then be used to infer proto-forms for data that has not been seen previously.

While scholars had been working on this problem before, a first impressive demonstration of the capability of machine learning methods was done by Meloni *et al.* (2021) for a test set in which Latin words needed to be reconstructed from words in several Romance languages. The authors used recurrent neural networks to learn to predict Latin word forms from word forms in the Romance languages. What was remarkable about their approach was the high accuracy reported. Using the edit distance (Levenshtein, 1966) to compare the proposed Latin word with the attested Latin word, their best parameter settings reported scores in which the proposed word would on average diverge less than one character from the attested word form. Kim *et al.* (2023) repeated the experiments by Meloni *et al.* (2021) but used Transformers (Vaswani *et al.*, 2017), the famous architecture for neural networks, that has

revolutionized artificial intelligence applications in many areas, but is best known in the context of large stochastic language models that are used to run chat bots. Not unexpectedly, the Transformer models further outperform the recurrent neural network architecture employed by Meloni *et al.* (2021).

The problem of supervised phonological reconstruction can be stated in the broader context of *reflex prediction*. Reflex prediction refers to the task of predicting how a word sounds when knowing the pronunciation of historically related words in related languages. For example, observing words like German *Zoll* and Swedish *tull* “customs”, I might predict that the English should have a corresponding words *toll* with a meaning similar (but not necessarily identical) to the meaning of the words in Swedish and German. At times, this may even work with language pairs, and as learners of languages closely related to languages we know intimately, we may even intuitively predict how certain words in the foreign language might sound, based on our knowledge of similar words in the languages we know.

We introduced the task in a preregistered study in which we first predicted word forms in languages that had so far been insufficiently studied and then checked the predictions against word forms verified in field work carried out after the predictions had been registered (Bodt & List, 2022). For the prediction, we used a supervised approach that goes back to a new method for the detection of regular sound correspondence patterns which I had introduced in 2019m. Having refined this approach in a later study, testing it on a larger collection of datasets from different language families (List *et al.*, 2022b), we used it as a baseline for a *shared task on reflex prediction* where we invited scholars with a background in machine learning and historical linguistics to design their own approaches for the task of reflex prediction (List *et al.*, 2022c). For this shared task, we used an even larger number of datasets from the Lexibank repository (List *et al.*, 2022a) and introduced a computer-assisted pipeline to make sure that all participants would have access to the data in the same form. The best systems were presented by Kirov *et al.* (2022) who used sophisticated neural network architectures and data processing pipelines to augment the very sparse input data. Interestingly, their best model was not based on transformers, but on convolutional network architectures originally designed for the task of restoring images (Liu *et al.*, 2018).

With respect to the originally proposed problem of *unsupervised phonological reconstruction*, not much has happened in the meantime. In 2013, Bouchard-Côté *et al.* (2013) showed that unsupervised automated phonological reconstruction is possible for Austronesian languages, using a complex framework in which stochastic transducers were applied to model the evolution of individual words across known reference trees. Since then, only Jäger (2019) has presented an alternative approach to the problem, in which methods for ancestral state reconstruction (Nunn, 2011, 63–89) were applied to a test set of Romance languages. The results were apparently disappointing, but closer inspection easily shows that the

problem is less the method itself (although a closer analysis would be needed), but even more the quality and the nature of the original data, which treats Latin as the ancestor of the Romance languages, although it has been known for a long time that a reconstruction of Romance languages cannot reveal Latin entirely, since many distinctions have been lost across all Romance languages (Hall, 1950).

In summary, we can conclude that the problem of automated phonological reconstruction remains a difficult problem for which no satisfying solutions exist so far. Even the very good results reported for the supervised reconstruction on Romance languages should be taken with considerable care, since the original dataset by Ciobanu & Dinu (2014) is far too large to provide a realistic test case that would be applicable to other language families. Not only does it seem impossible to find a comparable number of cognate sets for other language families of the same time depth as that of the Romance language family, I would also suspect that the majority of supposed cognates in the data do not qualify as true cognates (referring to etymologically related words, see Trask, 2000, 63) but rather reflect late borrowings from Latin into the individual Romance languages. Since borrowings show very different rules of transformation, which are – at least in the case of borrowings from Latin into Romance languages – often much simpler than the complex sound change processes that can be observed in the languages of the world, it would be important to test the approach by Meloni *et al.* (2021) and the follow-up approach by Kim *et al.* (2023) on the much sparser dataset that we proposed for our shared task on reflex prediction in order to understand their real potential.

Modeling problems

With respect to the modeling problems, there was – as far as I can judge – no substantial progress in the simulation of lexical change and sound change, but there were some interesting studies dealing with the problem of finding a statistical proof for language relatedness.

Ceolin (2019) tested the methods by Baxter and Manaster Ramer (2000), Kessler and Lehtonen (2006) and Kessler (2001) on a dataset consisting of six different language varieties, including Turkish, Mongolian, and Manchu, three languages that some scholars assume to be genetically related, showing that no conclusive results could be obtained in favor of the highly disputed Altaic language family (Georg, 2017).

Kassian *et al.* (2021) employed the test reported by Turchin *et al.* (2010), originally inspired by Dolgopolsky (1964) to another dataset of languages from the disputed Altaic family, with the difference that they used reconstructed proto-languages. Their test also failed to provide conclusive evidence for the whole language family, although they argue that rather clear support can be found for a deeper relationship of the families tested by Ceolin (2019). While both Ceolin (2019) and Kassian *et al.* (2021) applied methods proposed before to newly compiled datasets, Blevins and Sproat (2021) designed

a new workflow for to test for supposed deep language relations in order to find evidence for the hypothesis that the language isolate Basque is related to Indo-European. In contrast to previous studies, Blevins and Sproat (2021) test their approach on a rather large sample of languages where the language relations are known, showing that their approach is rather conservative, showing a tendency to reject grouping two languages within the same family in case of sparse evidence. Whether this is enough to prove the case of Basque and Indo-European, however, remains to be seen, since the data used in the test and the data used to test the potential relationship between Basque and Indo-European were not identical in design. This makes it more difficult to interpret the results of the test.

Given that Ceolin (2019) and Kassian *et al.* (2021) report contradicting results, both using methods that are supposed to deliver clear mathematical proofs, and given the difficulty to compare the evaluation study reported by Blevins and Sproat (2021) with the tests they conducted, I think it is safe to argue that the last word on the problem of finding a convincing statistical proof for language relatedness has not yet been spoken.

Analysis problems

No progress that I would be aware of has been made with respect to the establishment of first typologies for semantic change (Problem 8) and sound change (Problem 9). This confirms my original suspicion that both problems are indeed rather tough ones, requiring large amounts of annotated data – along with ideas of *how* the data should be annotated – that we simply do not have at the moment. Regarding the last problem on my list, the problem of establishing a typology of what I called *semantic promiscuity* by then, there has been no progress regarding the methodology of studying the phenomenon, but I think that there was at least some progress in explaining and defining the problem itself more properly. When I initially stated the problem, I was not aware of the rather large body of literature devoted to the topic of *lexical motivation*, referring to the process by which new words are created from existing ones (Koch, 2001; Koch & Marzo, 2007; Urban, 2016). Most of the words in the lexicon of human languages are composed from other words and individual word histories can be very complex, as can be seen from the illustration in Figure 2, where I have described, how the term *Ellenbogengesellschaft* in German (“dog-eat-dog society”, lit. “elbow society”) derives from individual words and suffixes. For a long time, I have been trying to find a way to investigate to which degree the meaning of individual words contributes to their reuse.

Geisler (2018) makes the rather strong claim that word reuse results from bodily experiences made in early life, such as the act of “falling” or “standing”. This could explain why words build from the verbal roots meaning “to fall” and “to stand” are so frequently met in German. An alternative possibility would be that word reuse reflects actual trends that could

Figure 2. The lexical motivation of the term “dog-eat-dog society” in German.

change over time (Alinei, 2001). This could explain, for example, the recent increase in the use of metaphors from psychology, popularly also known as “therapy speech” (Prendergast, 2022). Most likely, none of the two extreme positions is absolutely true. Instead, it is quite likely that both actual trends and important (potentially bodily) experiences contribute to the reuse of words in the world’s languages. But a detailed investigation of the semantics underlying these processes by which new words are formed from existing ones has so far not been carried out yet.

When I first stated my problem of establishing a typology of semantic promiscuity, I did not know that quite some detailed work on the processes of *lexical motivation* – albeit mostly qualitative in nature – had already been carried out and that some authors had proposed concepts quite similar to what I had in mind when proposing the term *semantic promiscuity*. Blank (1997, 21), for example, describes the processes of *attraction* and *expansion*. Attraction refers to cases where a given concept “attracts” different words to express it. In theory, we might be able to measure the *attractivity* of concepts, that is, their propensity to be expressed by multiple words. Expansion refers to cases where a word receives new meanings. If one agrees that the *expansivity* of words typically depends on the meaning they express originally, one could take this idea one step further and measure the *expansivity* of concepts and compare it across languages. Taking it one additional step further, one could then ask not only which concepts are good at triggering the extension of a word’s meaning, but also which concepts are good at triggering the reuse of a word in word formation processes, which is what I meant to denote with the term “semantic promiscuity”.

In a recent study in which I proposed new methods for the automated inference of words that share certain parts resulting from word formation processes (called *partial colexifications* in that study, see List, 2023), I found that there is a tendency for words expressing certain concepts to be reused much more

frequently in other words than words expressing different concepts. I also found a tendency for certain concepts to be expressed by words that are composed rather than being expressed by single morphemes. Since my analyses are based on a very rough approach that has not yet been tested any further so far, they should be taken with certain care. Given the confusion that the term “semantic promiscuity” has created in discussions with colleagues as well as in discussions following my original blog post (List, 2019c), I decided – inspired by a comment of Alexandre François – to use the term “lexical root productivity” from now on, in order to refer to the reuse potential of words in the lexicon – resulting from their meaning.

Regarding the problem of establishing a typology of lexical root productivity, I would no longer consider this as the most important problem for the field of lexical typology. Instead, I think, that one could state the problem in broader terms as the problem of establishing a typology of processes of *lexical motivation* that would allow us to investigate both how words are reused across the languages in the world (form-based perspective), and how concepts are expressed with the help of reusing lexical material (concept-based perspective). Despite earlier attempts to solve certain aspects of this problem (Urban, 2012), a real typology of lexical motivation has not yet been established, and the problem can therefore be considered as an unsolved one.

Outlook

In the end of 2018, I identified ten unsolved problems in computational historical linguistics that I considered as important and solvable at the same time. While quite some progress has been made in the past five years, most of the problems are still not solved, and it is not clear if and when we will find solutions for them. In order to be able to compare where I see the field of computational historical linguistics now, five years later, I have created a revised list of open problems, which is shown in Table 3. In two cases (Problem 3, contact layer detection,

Table 3. Updated list of open problems in computational historical linguistics.

No.	Problem (2019)	Problem (2023)	Progress
1	automated morpheme segmentation		-
2	automated sound law induction		-
3	automated borrowing detection	contact layer detection	+
4	automated phonological reconstruction		+
5	simulation of lexical change		-
6	simulation of sound change		-
7	statistical proof of language relatedness		(+)
8	typology of semantic change		-
9	typology of sound change		-
10	typology of semantic promiscuity	typology of lexical motivation	(+)

and Problem 10, typology of lexical motivation), I have decided to shift the focus and therefore modified the title of the problem. In two out of ten problems (Problem 3, automated borrowing detection, and Problem 4, automated phonological reconstruction), I would argue that some substantial progress has been made in the field, although I do not consider any of the problems as “solved” as of today.

Given that my optimism from 2018, when I assumed that most problems could be solved in five to ten years’ time, has not turned out to be very reliable, I would now refrain from making any further assumptions on whether the ten problems outlined in [Table 3](#) are solvable or not. If, however, in five years from now, the progress of the field of historical computational linguistics has been at a similar rate as it has been in the past five years, I assume that we will see some

substantial progress, even if none of the problems can be solved completely.

Data and software availability

Source data

No data are associated with this study.

Software availability

No software are required for this study.

Acknowledgments

I would like to thank Nathan W. Hill for ongoing interesting discussions on open problems in historical linguistics, and Russell D. Gray for introducing me to the fascinating world of open problems in science.

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Open Peer Review

Current Peer Review Status:

Version 1

Reviewer Report 13 February 2024

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.18157.r37453>

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Siva Kalyan

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This essay starts by reflecting on the importance of open problems in setting research priorities in a scientific discipline, and points out the large difference between what non-linguists consider to be important questions about language (e.g. how “big” a language is) and what linguists consider to be important questions about language.

The author then reviews preceding attempts to list the open problems in historical linguistics, and finds them all to be unsatisfying, as they do not translate into concrete research questions.

The author then introduces his own list of ten open problems in computational historical linguistics, which he announced in January 2019. He reviews the progress that has been made on each of the ten problems since then, and concludes while there has been substantial progress towards solving two of the problems (automated borrowing detection and automated phonological reconstruction), the problems are far from being solved. He also revises the formulation of two of the problems, to better reflect his understanding of the field.

Overall, I find the first three sections a bit lengthy, and would prefer the author’s list of open problems to be introduced sooner. However, if the audience for this essay includes non-linguists (or non-historical linguists), then the first three sections contain valuable background information.

My only suggestion for improvement is that the replacement of the term “semantic promiscuity” with “lexical root productivity” should be introduced earlier, since the former term is very confusing, and especially so for non-linguists.

Is the topic of the essay discussed accurately in the context of the current literature?

Yes

Is the work clearly and cogently presented?

Yes

Is the argument persuasive and supported by appropriate evidence?

Yes

Does the essay contribute to the cultural, historical, social understanding of the field?

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Computational historical linguistics

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard.

Reviewer Report 31 January 2024

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.18157.r37450>

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Thomas Brochhagen

Universitat Pompeu Fabra, Barcelona, Catalonia, Spain

This work discusses motivations and progress made toward addressing ten problems in historical computational linguistics, originally proposed by the author five years ago. I see the contribution as twofold. On the one hand, as argued within, there is use in taking a step back and evaluating where the field stands; what challenges it faces; and how they may be solved. On the other, after establishing a set of challenges, there is worth in iteratively looking back and evaluating to which extent these challenges have been solved; adjusting the problems and their framing as necessary.

Overall, I believe the manuscript in its present form already convincingly achieves the above so I'll just raise a few minor issues for the consideration:

1. I believe the Introduction is too pessimistic. First, while the ban from the Societe de Linguistique de Paris may have had its impact and is striking in its own right, it was abandoned within a decade and is best judged in the historical context it happened in (see, e.g., https://doi.org/10.1142/9789814401500_0133 for pointers). Second, and more importantly, much interesting and productive research on the evolution of language (both in terms of its emerge and in terms of the dynamics of change involved) has been conducted in the last decades. It may be that many proposals/models will turn out to be wrong in one way or another but, as I see it, that's the currency of science. The tone of the manuscript (particularly around the 4th paragraph) struck me as dismissive and as a bit of caricature. We can agree that there is outrageous speculation in the field, but I don't think this area of research is unique in this respect. I'd encourage the author to elaborate more on their stance, if it is indeed as pessimistic as it sounds in the current version,

or to consider attenuating this part a little.

2. There is little to no discussion on "automated morpheme segmentation". I found this curious considering that (i) subword tokenization is an important component of the NLP-pipeline of all successful Large Language Models, which are also increasingly becoming multilingual (see, e.g., mT5 [<https://github.com/google-research/multilingual-t5>] or BigScience's Bloom [<https://bigscience.huggingface.co/blog/bloom>]); and that (ii) since 2019 morpheme segmentation has, for instance, figured as a shared task in the Special Interest Group on Computational Morphology and Phonology (<https://sigmorphon.github.io/sharedtasks/>). It may be that these NLP-oriented approaches are not what the author had in mind since they are often not linguistically motivated. But they do fit the manuscript's preference for unsupervised solutions. I was left wondering what they lack to not even be considered solutions toward the challenge.

3. I concur with the Jeff Good (<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.18157.r36345>) that (i) the manuscript would benefit from careful proofreading to eliminate mistakes (e.g., "[...] we may easily loose the chance us to enrich our [...]" on p. 4) and that, in particular, (ii) Figure 2 would benefit from some further context to be interpreted as intended, either in the caption or in the text.

Is the topic of the essay discussed accurately in the context of the current literature?

Yes

Is the work clearly and cogently presented?

Yes

Is the argument persuasive and supported by appropriate evidence?

Yes

Does the essay contribute to the cultural, historical, social understanding of the field?

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: computational cognitive modelling; Bayesian methods; lexical typology

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard.

Reviewer Report 08 January 2024

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.18157.r36345>

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Jeff Good

University of Buffalo, Buffalo, USA

The core of this paper provides an update on progress towards a solution to ten problems in computational historical linguistics that were proposed by the author in 2018/2019. It additionally provides more general discussion of the role of problems in advancing scientific research following the tradition of Hilbert's problems in mathematics, and much of the framing of the contribution of the paper is in terms of "big picture" questions about problems in science even if the problems outlined for computational historical linguistics in the paper are somewhat narrower in scope. The paper is somewhat unusual in the context of linguistics due to personal nature of the rhetorical framing. However, this seems reasonable since it is being submitted under the category of "essay".

Because the author has already made substantial contributions to computational historical linguistics, I believe that it would be good to see this essay accepted in some form since his ideas about major problems in this area should be of general interest, though I would recommend certain changes. Most of these represent relatively minor issues centering around clarification of the manuscript, but two are more significant. I'll discuss those first.

More significant issues:

1. As discussed above, the focus of the paper is the ten problems in computational historical linguistics that were proposed by the author in 2018/2019. While a revised set of problems is presented here, this set is still more or less based on the original set. I think, in a paper like this, it would be beneficial for the author to also consider whether he would still propose the same basic ten problems proposed in 2018/2019 as being the most significant problems today. Perhaps, for example, some of them seem less important now than they did before, and there are only (say) eight "key" problems in his view. Or, perhaps, there is an eleventh problem he thinks should be added.

2. I think that, for the arguments of the paper to be clearly interpretable, it would be important for there to be a clear definition of what the author believes "computational historical linguistics" is, what its key goals are, and what model it assumes for "language" and "language change". In practice, for example, my sense is that most work in computational historical linguistics has, as its key goal, linguistic reconstruction, and this is suggested by work such as Jaeger (2019). Achieving this goal also means arriving at a better understanding of language change, but that does not usually seem to be the main goal of such work but, rather, a means of achieving the goal of reconstruction. Put differently, computational historical linguistics seems to emphasize the reconstruction of prehistory more than, for example, developing universal theories of sound change. I have no particular idea regarding what "computational historical linguistics" should include (or not include), but I do think it would be good for a paper like this one to take a clear position on this.

Minor issues:

- I noted various minor typos in the manuscript. Before it is accepted, it should be proofread carefully.

- "Non-linguists are often very surprised that asking for the origin of language is a taboo question in the field of historical linguistics." I don't have the impression that this is a taboo anymore. Rather, my sense is that it is understood to be outside of the domain of much of historical linguistics which is focused on how languages changed after language (as we understand it) had developed. This is, in large part because that's what the methods of historical linguistics are designed to investigate. The evolution of language is now studied, of course, but it tends to be done outside of historical linguistics in a narrow sense.

-The summary given of Weinreich et al.'s (1968, 183–187) problems does not fully match my reading of that work. For example, I don't read the "evaluation problem" as involving the degree to which change happens "consciously" but, rather, as whether language communities are aware that a change is taking place (even if it is originating in an unconscious way). I think it would be good to double check this summary. Similarly, I have always interpreted the "actuation problem" as being a version of "why do languages change". Maybe the author is correct in saying that this is not the case, but double checking the interpretation would still be a good idea in my view.

-"The failure to distinguish questions pertaining to particular languages and questions pertaining to language in general has led to many misunderstandings in the field of comparative linguistics." Can some examples be cited here?

-Table 2: I don't understand how automated morpheme segmentation is a historical computational problem rather than a general linguistic one. Can that be clarified?

-Figure 1: Can the interpretation of 20 x, 10 x, and 5x be explicitly explained in the text?

-"As an example for this procedure, consider the problem of cognate detection, the detection of historically related – or homologous – words across languages." This paper seems to be aimed at a general audience, not linguistic specialists. If so, I think the description of the concept of cognate needs to be expanded since it is discipline specific.

-"Based on this evolutionary model, we can then conclude that similar words observed across different language varieties have been inherited from the common, formerly unified, ancestral variety." Given that the paper opens with a discussion of the question of the evolution of language (from non-language), it might be best to avoid the term "evolutionary model" here since "evolution" has an ambiguous meaning in historical linguistics.

-"...but it requires a model of language relatedness that can then be tested against a random model in which languages are thought to be unrelated.": What is meant by "language relatedness"? It seems like what is meant is "genealogical relatedness under so-called normal transmission" (as opposed to, say, sharing features through contact). I think it would be good to make that explicit.

-"While there are numerous attempts in the literature to come up with a convincing statistical model to prove genetic relationship..." (footnote 5): I would add Nichols (1996) to this list.

-"Rather huge progress – at least when looking back specifically at the last couple of years – has been made with respect to supervised phonological reconstruction.": I think it would be useful to

say something about the supervision involved in these approaches.

-"While scholars had been working on this problem before, a first impressive demonstration of the capability of machine learning methods...": I think that it is worth mentioning that these are of a different character than other approaches since there is the so-called "black box" effect with them. That is, they may work well, but we don't really know why. This is opposed to computational models that require an amount of computation that would be practically impossible for humans to conduct by hand, but where each step in the process is known and understood.

-"I identified ten unsolved problems in computational historical linguistics that I considered as important and solvable at the same time." Following on from my general comment above, would the author still consider all of these important (or as important) today?

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Is the topic of the essay discussed accurately in the context of the current literature?

Yes

Is the work clearly and cogently presented?

Yes

Is the argument persuasive and supported by appropriate evidence?

Yes

Does the essay contribute to the cultural, historical, social understanding of the field?

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: linguistics, historical linguistics, linguistic typology

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.
